

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF AN INSTRUMENT TO MEASURE THE TEACHERS' READINESS, COMPETENCE, AND PRACTICES TOWARDS INTERNATIONAL LARGE-SCALE ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to develop and validate the survey instruments utilized to measure teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment. This study was research and development (R&D) implementing the ADDIE model. However, this study was limited to the test of validity and reliability. There were five indicators for each that measures the constructs of teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment. Based on the data analysis, it was found that the test of validity using Aiken's V formula of teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment instrument established highly valid which was indicates suitable for use because it has been fulfilled aspects of clarity and direction of items, presentation and organization of items, suitability of items, adequateness of the content, attainment of the purpose, objective, scale, and evaluation of rating; the test of reliability of established excellent which was appropriate to be used to assess teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment. From the research finding, it can be concluded that the survey questionnaire is valid and very reliable to measure the teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment.

Keywords: *International Large-Scale Assessment; Competence; Practices; Readiness, Teachers'*

INTRODUCTION

Assessment plays a vital role in any reform. It is conducted to evaluate the needs for a reform, identify the kind of reforms needed, monitor the implementation of the reform, measure the effects, and assess the effectiveness of the whole reform to ensure that the investment is worthwhile. In education, assessment is often used for three different purposes – assessment for learning, assessment as learning, and assessment for learning. While the role of assessment in improving education is vital, there are several critical aspects of education that matter most for student learning. These key factors include well-prepared teachers, well-designed and coherent curriculum, skillful instruction that is adapted to students' needs, and personalized learning environments in which students are well-known by their teachers (Samosa & Navarro, 2024). Providing these key features of a sound education is a major foundation of an accountability system.

Taking aside, types of assessment practices and assessment competence are the defining part of collecting information to improve the student's learning ability (Mutlu, 2020). Assessment of the learners' is a vital part of teaching since it enables teachers to fully understand the capabilities of their students and to develop appropriate instructional strategies that positively influence academic learning (Mills, 2022).

As such, international large-scale assessments (ILSA) are considered an important tool for studying education systems and for formulating evidence-based policies, some researchers argue that “the use of international assessment data can result in a range of unintended consequences, such as the shaping and governing of school systems ‘by numbers’” (Johansson, 2020). Some major international large-scale assessments (ILSA) include the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), and the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS).

Espinosa, et al, (2023) identified four models of motivation driving countries to participate in the ILSA studies: (1) the financial aid model; (2) the macro-dissatisfaction perspective; (3) the policy diffusion model; and (4) the rational choice model. In the case of the Philippines, the Department of Education seems to be motivated by the rational choice model. Malaluan (2021) stated that the “objective in participating in PISA was to look in the mirror and find out how our learners compared with the rest of the world, and to generate important data to deepen our understanding of the major factors that impact student performance”. The Philippines' participation in ILSA is explicitly spelled out in the country's Department of Education's Policy Guidelines on System Assessment Policy in the K to 12 Basic Education Program (DepEd, 2017). The Philippines joined the PISA

2018, the first ILSA the country participated in since the current K to 12 Basic Education Program was implemented.

However, previous studies highlighted several issues related to teachers and their classroom assessment practices. These include inadequate knowledge of fundamental assessment and measurement concepts (Bichay-Awadalla & Bulotsky-Shearer, 2022), inadequate training in assessment (Samosa, 2022) and failure of teachers to correctly utilize the guidelines for the learners in assessment courses (Di Liberto et al., 2022).

Looking on the literature evidences the lack of to measure teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment. There is an evident lack of research that investigates instruments to measure teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment.

Research Objectives

To test the validity and reliability of the teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment and the relevance of this questionnaire.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized research and development (R&D) intended to produce an instrument for teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale

Figure 1:
ADDIE MODEL OF RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT DESIGN OF THE STUDY

assessment. The development model applied in this study was ADDIE model which consists of the stage of Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation. The studied was limited to the analysis, design, development, validation, and reliability stages from expert judgement.

PROCEDURES

Stage 1 Analysis, it included the problem analysis and needs analysis of the teachers, analysis of indicators for teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment.

The analysis of teachers' needs included analyzing the importance of teachers' readiness, competence and practices development based on the towards international large-scale assessment. Then, the analysis of teachers' readiness, competence and practices indicators consisted of analysis of expert opinions towards international large-scale assessment listed in scientific articles.

Stage 2 Design, the researcher designed the method of assessment instruments. The design was started from defining the indicator, which was used as a recommendation in developing the instruments. Then, the instrument was equipped with a scoring technique; therefore, the design of the scoring technique was defined based on the form of the instrument to be developed.

Stage 3 Development, at this stage, the researcher developed the 4- Likert scale that based on several aspects, indicators, and domains. These instruments were validated by experts based on the aspects of clarity and direction of items, presentation and organization of items, suitability of items, adequateness of the content, attainment of the purpose, objective, scale, and evaluation of rating. The validators provided advice and inputs on the instruments to improve a valid instrument. As a result, a valid instrument could be used to assess the teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment.

SAMPLE & SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

The sample of this study were thirty (30) science teachers who joined in in the international large-scale assessment in province of Bulacan. Before the actual survey conducted, pilot studies were conducted to test the reliability and validity of the research instrument to use. This is to prevent confusion and identify the weaknesses of the built-in items (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Five (5) science experts with doctorate degree in

science underwent face validation on the research instruments. To answer the reliability of this instrument, a total of thirty (30) samples were randomly selected. Research scholar and test experts recommend a pilot study sample between 10 and 30 respondents or need to exceed 20 (Samosa & Dantay, 2023). Random sampling is chosen to respond to the instruments constructed and involve samples from various angles and areas (Creswell & Clark, 2017).

DATA ANALYSIS

The techniques of quantitative data analysis were used to analyze the indicators of teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment based on the results of validation from 4 experts. In this study, the data analysis was explained descriptively. The analysis stage began with the validation by experts regarding the aspects of clarity and direction of items, presentation and organization of items, suitability of items, adequateness of the content, attainment of the purpose, objective, scale, and evaluation of rating. The validation was conducted by giving a questionnaire to the experts. Then, the validators were also asked to provide suggestions and inputs to revise the deficiencies in the instrument. The results of validation were analyzed using Aiken's V. If the value of Aiken's V was lower than the minimum value of Aiken's V, the item was considered invalid. The items that were declared valid were revised based on the notes provided by the validators. The formula is presented below:

$$V = \frac{\sum S}{[n(c - 1)]}$$

Note:

V = Validity Aiken

S = r – lo

lo = the lowest validity rating score

c = the highest validity rating score

r = score given by validator n = number of validators

Table 1
Validity Aiken

The value of V	Interpretation
$0.80 < V \leq 1.00$	Very high
$0.60 < V \leq 0.80$	High
$0.40 < V \leq 0.60$	Adequate
$0.20 < V \leq 0.40$	Low
$0.00 < V \leq 0.20$	Very low

The validation of the teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale was measured by utilizing 4 – Likert scale validation form. This was performed by giving checklist on the choice by expert validators. In addition, there was also a space for the expert validators to write inputs/ suggestions on this validation sheet. The 4 – Likert scale validation form is displayed in Table 2.

Table 2
Rating Description of Face Validation

Rating	Interval	Interpretation	Description
4	3.28 – 4.00	Highly Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for investigation, allowing 0 – 5% error.
3	2.52 – 3.27	Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for investigation, allowing 6 - 10% error.
2	1.76 – 2.51	Less Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for investigation, allowing 11 – 20% error.
1	1.00 – 1.75	Not Valid at all	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for investigation, allowing more than 20% error.

After that, the collected data were analyzed by using descriptive statistical analysis techniques. The data were processed through numbers in the form of weighted mean.

After the validity was established, it was pilot tested for thirty (30) teacher-respondents to determine its reliability. Using Cronbach's alpha, the instruments were tested it reliability. Alpha Test of Reliability. All noted discrepancies or vague statements on the instruments were integrated and incorporated in the finalization of the instrument. Cronbach's alpha is a measure of internal consistency that is calculated using sample variance, total scores, and number of items. Cronbach's alpha is used to assess how consistently multiple items in a survey or test assess the same skill or characteristic. Higher values of Cronbach's alpha suggest higher internal consistency. The Cronbach's alpha scale is displayed in Table 3. The formula is presented below:

$$\alpha = \frac{N * \bar{c}}{\bar{v} + (N - 1) * \bar{c}}$$

Where:

N = number of items

\bar{c} = mean covariance between items.

\bar{v} = mean item variance.

Table 3
Cronbach's alpha Reliability

The value of Cronbach's alpha	Internal Consistency
$\alpha \leq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.70$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.60$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.50$	Poor
$0.50 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

Once all the necessary procedures for validity and reliability have been taken into consideration, the research checklist-questionnaire will then be finalized.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

This portion discusses the findings obtained from the test of validity and reliability of developed survey instruments. Furthermore, it interprets and analyzes data gathered based on survey – questionnaires given to the -respondents.

Analysis of Phase

Stages of developing the instrument started with an initial analysis and the needs of teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large – scale assessment. After the reading of literature and studies focuses on the international large assessments results in science (OECD, 2019; Belmi, & Mangali, 2020; Balagtas, et al., 2020; & Balagtas, 2021) factor that may be attributed to the low international large – scale assessment ranking of the Philippines is the mode of test administration was facilitated through a computer-based test to be accomplished in two hours. The implication of computer-based assessment in large-scale testing revealed that anxiety levels of learners' increase when they know that they are being monitored while using computers in answering tests. More so, the learning competencies in the K to12 Science Curriculum are not proportionately and appropriately distributed across grade levels in terms of cognitive demand as there is a high concentration of learning competencies that involve tasks of low-level cognitive demand and the lack of explicit inclusion of topics in Earth and Space Systems (Belmi, & Mangali, 2020). From this, identified competencies, it was necessary to include in the instruments to measure the teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards alignment of the content and objective from MATATAG Curriculum to international large-scale assessments and the skills in computer-based assessment.

The analysis of the indicators of the teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment

The analysis of survey instruments was carried out by selecting competencies that measures teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment that would be developed for the assessment instruments. The following are the definitions of the constructs that measure teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment.

Table 4
Teacher Readiness

Constructs	Definitions
Teacher Readiness	The degree of how good and confident the teachers are in conducting learning assessments aligned with large – scale assessments.
Attainment of Objectives	Targets which specify the knowledge, understanding and skills related to mathematics that learners are expected to have acquired by the end of assessments against a predetermined set of criteria which is clearly articulated levels specifying the degree of proficiency to be attained.
Participation of Learners and Teachers	The learners and teachers being active and engaged, impacting on curriculum innovation implemented; and feeling of belonging to the attainment of science performance.
Utilization of Strategies	It is a systematic approach to the process and use of different assessment tools and mechanisms to aide in the learning process that provides learners to participate, connect, and add excitement to the content being delivered.
Test Results	It provides what the learners have learned what they are expected to learn, such as whether they have met state learning standards which also identify gaps in learners' learning and academic progress.
Utilization of Instructional Materials	It is aspects that are taken into account the use of Instructional delivery and design to gain acceptance, implement, and institutionalize a program of instruction of content from the teaching and learning process.

Table 5
Teacher Competence

Constructs	Definitions
Teacher Competence	It refers to the ability of teachers to design, implement, and interpret assessments effectively and ethically. In this study, it is the ability of the science teachers' capacity to select appropriate assessment methods, develop valid and reliable assessment instruments, analyze and interpret assessment data, and use assessment results to inform instruction and decision-making. It is extending science teachers to evaluate the knowledge, skills, and performance of others in a fair, accurate, and meaningful manner.
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	<p>Content Knowledge. It is used when referring to the contained thing as an undifferentiated whole. In the study what is considered as content are the parts of a full-length execution of a lesson through a daily lesson plan or the contents of an evaluation tool.</p> <p>Pedagogy. It is most understood as the approach to teaching, refers to the theory and practice of learning, and how this process influences, and is influenced by, the social, political, and psychological development of learners. In the study, pedagogy is a vital component in rating science teacher's competence.</p>
Learning Environment	This refers to the diverse physical locations, contexts, and cultures in which students learn. In the study, learning environment is one of the key competences that teachers need to assess to say whether or not they are competent in performing their mandate as public school teachers.
Diversity of Learning	It is the infinite variety of life experiences and attributes a child brings to their formal learning at school that teachers seek to meet the needs of all learners, so that every student experience success.
Curriculum and Planning	<p>Curriculum. Referring to the lessons and academic content taught in a school or in a specific course or program. In the study, an individual teacher's curriculum, for example, would be the specific learning standards, lessons, assignments, and materials used to organize and teach a particular course. All these make up a curriculum.</p> <p>Planning. It is the process of thinking about the activities required to achieve a desired goal. It is used in study as the first and foremost activity to achieve desired results. It involves the creation and maintenance of a plan, such as psychological aspects that require conceptual skills.</p>

Assessment and Reporting

Assessment. The activities and instruments used by the teacher in monitoring the progress and measuring the learning of the students.

Reporting. It is the presentation of honest, credible and impartial information. In the study, reporting has to do with making certain stakeholders like that of the parents inform them about the progress of their children in school.

Professional Development

It is learning to earn or maintain professional credentials such as academic degrees to formal coursework, attending conferences, and informal learning opportunities situated in practice. In the study, it has been described as intensive and collaborative, ideally incorporating an evaluative stage.

Community Linkages

It refers to the connections and relationships established between individuals, organizations, and communities to promote collaboration and resource. It is expected that science teachers to identify and respond to opportunities that link teaching and learning in the classroom to the experiences, interests and aspirations of the wider school community and other key stakeholders. In this study, it concerns the importance of science teachers' understanding and fulfilling their obligations in upholding professional ethics, accountability and transparency to promote professional and harmonious relationships with learners, parents, schools and the wider community.

Table 6
Teacher Practices

Constructs	Definitions
Teacher Practices	The degree of how good and confident the teachers are in conducting learning assessments aligned with large – scale assessments.
Planning for Assessment	The set of guidelines or steps followed by the teacher-respondents in designing and developing the assessment tasks.
Collection of Learning Evidence	The assessment practices, both formative and summative, are done by the teacher-respondents in determining the learning status and monitoring the learning progress of their learners.
Interpretation and Communication of Evidence	The practices of the teacher-respondents in: (1) analyzing and making sense of the data collected from the assessment tasks; and (2) reporting the results to the learners and parents.
Support Provided to Engage Students Actively	The assessment practices of the teacher-respondents in motivating the learners and ensuring that learning will take place through assessment tasks.
Learning Contents Assessed	It is the learning competencies and specific learning objectives covered by the topics discussed by the teacher.
Application of Assessment Evidence	The impact of the evidence collected from the assessment methods and how it affects future instruction and assessments in terms of planning and decision making.

Designing and Development Stage

Based on the problem analysis and needs analysis results, it was revealed that developing an instrument to assess the teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment was required. At this stage, the questions were developed consisting of series of items for the purpose of gathering information from the respondents. The researcher used the 4 Likert scale questionnaire. This questionnaire has three (3) main portions.

Part I focuses on the extent readiness of science teachers towards international large-scale assessment in terms attainment of the objectives, participation of learners and teachers, utilization of different strategies, test results and utilization of learning materials with five (5) indicators for each variables considered. **Part II** focuses on the evaluation of

the level of science teachers' competence towards' international large-scale assessment in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, diversity of learning, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, professional development, and community linkages with five (5) indicators for each variables considered. **Part III** focuses on the extent practices of science teachers towards international large-scale assessment in terms of the following planning for assessment, collection of learning evidence, interpretation and communication of evidence, support provided to engages learners' actively, learning content assessed and application of assessment evidence with five (5) indicators considered. The 4 – Likert scale rating form is displayed in Table 2.

Table 7
Rating Description of Face Validation

Rating	Interval	Teachers' Readiness	Interpretation Teachers' Competence	Teachers' Practices
4	3.28 – 4.00	Low Extent	Low Competent	Not at all Practice
3	2.52 – 3.27	Moderately Extent	Moderately Competent	Somewhat Practice
2	1.76 – 2.51	Extent	Competent	Mostly Practice
1	1.00 – 1.75	Highly Extent	Highly Competent	Completely Practice

1. Results of Expert Validation and Test of Reliability

Table 4
Face Validity of Survey Instruments

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. Clarity and Direction of Items	3.36	Highly Valid
2. Presentation and Organization of Items	3.45	Highly Valid
3. Suitability of Items	3.16	Highly Valid
4. Adequateness of the Content	3.67	Highly Valid
5. Attainment of the Purpose	3.77	Highly Valid
6. Objective	3.48	Highly Valid
7. Scale and Evaluation of Rating	3.55	Highly Valid
Overall	3.44	Highly Valid

The results of expert validation on the aspects of clarity and direction of items, presentation and organization of items, suitability of items, adequateness of the content, attainment of the purpose, objective, scale, and evaluation of rating was showed in Figure 4.

As observed, it was shown that the validation in the aspect of clarity and direction of items was 3.36 which interpreted as highly valid. This result indicates that the instrument was in accordance with the material aspects. This indicates that the vocabulary level, language & structure are at the conceptual level of the respondents. More so, the test directions and the items are written in a clear and understandable manner. Taking aside, the assessed presentation and organization of items aspects was gained 3.45 and interpreted as highly valid. This indicates that items are well presented and organized in a logical manner. Meanwhile, in the aspects of suitability of items was yield of 3.16 and interpreted as highly valid. This indicated that the items were appropriately presented the substance/content of the research. More so the questions/items are designed to determine what are supposed to be measured. In a way, adequateness of the content aspects, it was gleaned a 3.67 which interpreted as highly valid. This denotes that the number of the questions/items per domain/area were enough to answer the questions needed for the research. Paramount to the aspect of attainment of the purpose obtained a 3.77 and interpreted as highly valid. This stipulated that the instrument could fulfill the objectives needed for the research. Concomitantly, objectives aspect, the results acquired a 3.48 and interpreted as highly valid. This showed that each item question/indicator can answer or measure specific behavior/problem. Looking forward to the scale and evaluation of rating aspect draw a 3.55 and interpreted as highly valid. Deemed the overall results of face validation of experts showed that 3.44 and interpreted as highly valid. Therefore, the whole items of the instrument got very high validity and were declared valid or feasible.

Table 5
Test of Validity and Reliability of Survey Instrument

Constructs		Validity		Reliability	
		V	Interpretation	α	Interpretation
TEACHERS'	Attainment of Objectives	0.93	Very high	0.92	Excellent
	Participation of Learners and Teachers	0.90	Very high	0.91	Excellent
	Utilization of Strategies	0.88	Very high	0.91	Excellent
	Test Results	0.85	Very high	0.91	Excellent
	Utilization of Instructional Materials	0.90	Very high	0.92	Excellent
	Overall	0.89	Very high	0.92	Excellent
TEACHERS' COMPETENCE	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	0.88	Very high	0.97	Excellent
	Learning Environment	0.97	Very high	0.97	Excellent
	Diversity of Learning	0.93	Very high	0.96	Excellent
	Curriculum and Planning	0.95	Very high	0.97	Excellent
	Assessment and Reporting	0.88	Very high	0.97	Excellent
	Professional Development	0.87	Very high	0.97	Excellent
	Community Linkages	0.92	Very high	0.97	Excellent
	Overall	0.91	Very high	0.97	Excellent

TEACHERS' PRACTICES	Planning for Assessment	0.98	Very high	0.92	Excellent
	Collection of Learning Evidence	0.92	Very high	0.91	Excellent
	Interpretation and Communication of Evidence	0.93	Very high	0.91	Excellent
	Support Provided to Engage Students Actively	0.90	Very high	0.91	Excellent
	Learning Contents Assessed	0.88	Very high	0.91	Excellent
	Application of Assessment Evidence	0.87	Very high	0.92	Excellent
Overall		0.91	Very high	0.92	Excellent

Table 5 illustrates the level where the validity and reliability is at a high level if the range of alpha values are between 0.87 to 0.98 as it is approaching the value of 1. On the other hand, if the alpha value is less than 0.6, this means that the level of reliability is low (Samosa & Dantay, 2023). The justification of the researcher conducting the pilot study is to examine the accuracy of the instrument because according to Navarro, Santos, & Corpuz (2019) there are three types of results obtained while conducting a pilot study. First, the data is reliable but invalid. Second, the data is valid but unreliable. Third, the data is valid and reliable. Yazon (2019) stated that the higher the value of reliability, the smaller the error found in the study instrument. Nevertheless, according to Suskie (2018) the validity of a study is not necessarily acceptable if the alpha value is high. Such problems could however be overcome by conducting the Test-Retest Reality analysis if the results of the pilot study were vague or the alpha values obtained were too low (de Guzman, & Adamos, 2015).

The results of the pilot study presented that the developed questionnaire for the survey done on the teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale was suitable based on test of validity and reliability.

Taking aside, the teachers' readiness towards international large-scale assessment survey – questionnaires established overall validity 0.89 were interpreted as very high and reliability of 0.92 described as excellent. Likewise, the sub variables of teacher readiness towards international large-scale established very high and excellent instrument includes the attainment of objectives ($V = 0.93$; $\alpha = 0.92$), Participation of Learners and Teachers ($V = 0.90$; $\alpha = 0.91$), Utilization of Strategies ($V = 0.88$; $\alpha = 0.91$), Test Results ($V = 0.85$; $\alpha = 0.91$), and Utilization of Instructional Materials ($V = 0.90$; $\alpha = 0.92$).

Cognizantly, the teachers' competence towards international large-scale assessment survey – questionnaires established overall validity 0.91 were interpreted as very high and reliability of 0.97 described as excellent. Moreover, the sub variables of

teachers' competence towards international large-scale obtained very high validity and excellent reliability includes the content knowledge and pedagogy ($V = 0.88$; $\alpha = 0.87$), learning environment ($V = 0.97$; $\alpha = 0.97$), diversity of learning ($V = 0.93$; $\alpha = 0.96$), curriculum and planning ($V = 0.95$; $\alpha = 0.97$), assessment and reporting ($V = 0.88$; $\alpha = 0.97$), Professional Development ($V = 0.87$; $\alpha = 0.97$), and Community Linkages ($V = 0.92$; $\alpha = 0.97$).

Emergently, the teachers' practices towards international large-scale assessment survey – questionnaires gained overall validity 0.91 were interpreted as very high and reliability of 0.92 described as excellent. Moreover, the sub variables of teachers' practices towards international large-scale obtained very high validity and excellent reliability includes planning for assessment. ($V = 0.88$; $\alpha = 0.97$), collection of learning evidence ($V = 0.92$; $\alpha = 0.91$), interpretation and communication of evidence ($V = 0.93$; $\alpha = 0.91$), support provided to engage students actively ($V = 0.90$; $\alpha = 0.91$), learning contents assessed ($V = 0.88$; $\alpha = 0.91$), and application of assessment evidence ($V = 0.87$; $\alpha = 0.91$).

Conclusions

Based on the results, it can be concluded that researcher involves the expert judgment to validate teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment instrument. The content validity testing result with the Aiken's V formula of teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment instrument shows that the instrument is suitable for use because it has been fulfilled aspects of clarity and direction of items, presentation and organization of items, suitability of items, adequateness of the content, attainment of the purpose, objective, scale, and evaluation of rating; the test of reliability of established excellent which was appropriate to be used to assess teachers' readiness, competence, and practices towards international large-scale assessment.

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APPENDIX

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

The undersigned is presently conducting test of validity and reliability of the survey entitled “**SCIENCE TEACHERS’ READINESS, COMPETENCE, AND PRACTICES TOWARDS INTERNATIONAL LARGE-SCALE ASSESSMENT**”. Kindly answer all items sincerely and honestly. Rest assured, that all your answer will be treated with utmost confidentiality. Thank you very much.

(Optional)_____

School: (Optional)_____

PART I. EXTENT READINESS OF SCIENCE TEACHERS TOWARDS INTERNATIONAL LARGE-SCALE ASSESSMENT

Direction: Below are the statements that focuses on the extent readiness of science teachers towards international large-scale assessment. Kindly put a check mark (✓) on the column that corresponds to your answer.

Rating	Interpretation
1	Low Extent
2	Moderately Extent
3	Extent
4	Highly Extent

No	Attainment of Objectives <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	improve scientific literacy skills of the K to 12 learners following the framework of international large – scale assessments (PISA, TIMSS, and SEA- PLM).				
2	strengthen teacher’s capability to teach and assess scientific literacy skills effectively.				
3	improve management and administration of the assessment aligned with the international large – scale assessments framework (PISA, & TIMSS).				
4	establish a school-based mentoring/learning partnership program thru SLAC.				
5	all K to 12 learners equipped with fundamental science skills and competencies needed for academic success in later key stages.				
No	Participation of Learners and Teachers <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	learn through participating in decisions within a wide variety of educational activities and processes leading to meaningful impacts and outcomes in mathematical skills.				
2	be involved in monitoring and evaluating the scientific literacy program aligned with the international large – scale assessments (PISA, & TIMSS) by participation and its impacts.				
3	be enabled to participate through a variety of ways of expressing their views.				
4	learn about their right to participate voluntarily in decision making.				
5	have a say in shaping educational provisions in their setting and beyond of the international large – scale assessments framework program (PISA, & TIMSS).				
No	Utilization of Strategies <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	build excellence in classroom practice in effective assessments.				
2	differentiate teaching to meet learners’ different learning needs.				
3	build instructional leadership in international large – scale assessments framework (PISA, & TIMSS).				
4	embed a whole-school focus on international large – scale assessments framework (PISA, & TIMSS).				

5	engage parents and carers as partners in improving learners' competencies international large – scale assessments framework (PISA, & TIMSS).				
No	Test Results <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	describe the status of the educational program.				
2	identify the knowledge and skills over which learners have (or do not have) mastery on the mathematical skills assessment.				
3	support judgments about the adequacy of observed performance in mathematical skills assessment.				
4	provide an argument about the success or failure of instructional content and strategies.				
5	reinforce the call for high academic standards and educational reform, and school accountability.				
No.	Utilization of Instructional Materials <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	arouse and sustain the interest and attention of the learners.				
2	concrete concepts and ideas to promote meaningful learning in mathematical skills assessments.				
3	provide self-activities for independent learning.				
4	increase the quality of learning while decreasing the time spent				
5	make learning more permanent by providing rich experiences in mathematical skills assessment.				

PART II. LEVEL OF SCIENCE TEACHERS' COMPETENCE TOWARDS' INTERNATIONAL LARGE-SCALE ASSESSMENT

Direction: Below are the statements that focuses on the level of science teachers' competence towards' international large-scale assessment. Kindly put a check mark (✓) on the column that corresponds to your answer.

Rating	Interpretation
1	Low Competent
2	Moderately Competent
3	Competent
4	Highly Competent

No	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
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1	demonstrate content knowledge and its application within and/or across curriculum teaching areas.				
2	demonstrate an understanding of research - based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning.				
3	show skills in the positive use of ICT to facilitate the teaching and learning process.				
4	demonstrate knowledge of teaching strategies that promote literacy and numeracy skills.				
5	apply teaching strategies that develop critical and creative thinking, and/or other higher-order thinking skills.				
No	Learning Environment <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	demonstrate knowledge of policies, guidelines and procedures that provide safe and secure learning environments.				
2	demonstrate understanding of learning environments that promote fairness, respect and care to encourage learning.				
3	demonstrate knowledge of positive and non-violent discipline in the management of learner behavior and managing classroom structure that engages learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within the available physical learning environments.				
4	demonstrate understanding of supportive learning environments that nurture and inspire learner participation.				
5	demonstrate knowledge of learning environments that motivate learners to work productively by assuming responsibility for their own learning.				
No	Diversity of Learning <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	demonstrate knowledge and understanding of differentiated teaching to suit the learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences.				
2	implement teaching strategies that are responsive to the learners' linguistic, cultural, socio-economic, and religious backgrounds.				
3	use strategies responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness and talents.				
4	demonstrate understanding of the special educational needs of learners in difficult circumstances, including geographic isolation; chronic illness; displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement or disasters; child abuse and child labor practices.				
5	demonstrate knowledge of teaching strategies that are inclusive of learners from indigenous groups.				
No	Curriculum and Planning	1	2	3	4

	<i>As a teacher I can</i>				
1	prepare developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements.				
2	identify learning outcomes that are aligned with learning competencies.				
3	demonstrate knowledge of the implementation of relevant and responsive learning programs.				
4	seek advice concerning strategies that can enrich teaching practice.				
5	show skills in the selection, development, and use of a variety of teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.				
No	Assessment and Reporting <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	demonstrate knowledge of the design, selection, organization and use of diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.				
2	demonstrate knowledge of monitoring and evaluation of learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data.				
3	demonstrate knowledge of providing timely, accurate and constructive feedback to improve learner performance.				
4	demonstrate familiarity with a range of strategies for communicating learner needs, progress, and achievement.				
5	demonstrate an understanding of the role of assessment data as feedback in teaching and learning practices and programs.				
No	Professional Development <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	articulate a personal philosophy of teaching that is learner centered.				
2	demonstrate behaviors that uphold the dignity of teaching as a profession by exhibiting qualities such as caring attitude, respect, and integrity.				
3	seek opportunities to establish professional links with colleagues.				
4	demonstrate an understanding of how professional reflection and learning can be used to improve practice.				
5	demonstrate motivation to realize professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers.				
No	Community Linkages <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4

1	demonstrate an understanding of knowledge of learning environments that are responsive to community contexts.				
2	seek advice concerning strategies that build relationships with parents/guardians and the wider community.				
3	demonstrate awareness of existing laws and regulations that apply to the teaching profession and become familiar with the responsibilities specified in the code of ethics for professional teachers				
4	demonstrate knowledge and understanding of school policies and procedures to foster harmonious relationships with the wider school community.				
5	Learning best practices for a good relationship among school, home, and community.				

PART III. EXTENT PRACTICES OF SCIENCE TEACHERS TOWARDS INTERNATIONAL LARGE-SCALE ASSESSMENT

Direction: Below are the statements that focuses on the extent practices of science teachers towards international large-scale assessment. Kindly put a check mark (√) on the column that corresponds to your answer.

Rating	Interpretation
1	Not at all Practice
2	Somewhat Practice
3	Mostly Practice
4	Completely Practice

No.	Planning for Assessment	1	2	3	4
	<i>As a teacher I can</i>				
1	share the expected learning outcomes to the learners so they are informed of what is expected on them.				
2	align the assessment tasks with the content standards, performance standards, most essential learning competencies, and specific learning objectives.				
3	consider the learning style and multiple intelligence of the learners in designing online assessments.				
4	collaborate with colleagues to come up with an assessment task that integrates the competencies of two or more learning areas.				
5	develop appropriate marking keys or rubrics to be used in the assessment task.				
No.	Collection of Learning Evidence	1	2	3	4

	<i>As a teacher I can</i>				
1	give pre-test to identify the learning needs of the learners before instruction and post-test to measure the learning gained after instruction.				
2	conduct plenty of formative assessments to prepare the learners for summative assessment.				
3	provide learners with mock exams so they can experience what is required for summative assessment.				
4	administer summative assessment at the end of each unit or chapter.				
5	use portfolio assessment or other forms of authentic assessments.				
No.	Interpretation and Communication of Evidence <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	return scores and corrected outputs with appropriate feedback promptly.				
2	communicate the learner's strengths and weaknesses based on assessment results to the parents or guardians.				
3	discuss the assessment results and academic progress to the learners so they can reflect on their good as well as poor study habits.				
4	use learning management system (LMS) in releasing scores and grades so the learners and their parents/guardians have a quick access to the assessment results and can easily monitor them.				
5	use online learning platforms where the students can get assessment feedback in real time.				
No.	Support Provided to Engage Students Actively <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	develop and assign tasks that are sufficiently flexible for students to tailor them to their own needs and interests.				
2	adjust assessment to develop learners' responsibility for their learning.				
3	give contingent, specific, and credible praise and feedback.				
4	develop and assign assessment tasks where the learners can work collaboratively with their peers.				
5	connect assessments with real-life scenarios.				
No	Learning Contents Assessed <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	design summative assessment that covers the topic/s taught.				
2	design assessment tasks that are aligned with Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) and learning objectives of the subject matter.				

3	provide a shortlist of possible topics and give the learners chance to select a topic for their essay or project.				
4	design assessment task that encompasses all learning domains (knowledge, skills, values).				
5	create an assessment task that measures interdisciplinary contents and competencies.				
No	Application of Assessment Evidence <i>As a teacher I can</i>	1	2	3	4
1	administer a parallel test to test the reliability of summative assessment scores (e.g., compare the result of pre-test and post-test).				
2	reflect on one's assessment practices using the assessment information gathered and feedback from the students.				
3	revise summative test based on test item analysis.				
4	analyze assessment information gathered before, during, and after instruction to understand each students' progress to date and to inform future instructional planning.				
5	record and report assessment result for school-level analysis, evaluation, and decision making.				
